

METAPHOR IN LINGUISTIC RESEARCH

МЕТАФОРА В ЛИНГВИСТИЧЕСКИХ ИССЛЕДОВАНИЯХ

TILSHUNOSLIK TADQIQOTLARIDA METAFORA

Tuychiboyev Ikrom Bahodir o'g'li

Gulistan State Pedagogical Institute

Researcher.ikromtuychibev96@gmail.com, +998915039609

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ABSTRACT. This article explores the multifaceted nature of metaphor through various theoretical perspectives, including cognitive, pragmatic, conflict, anomaly, and interaction theories. It highlights the evolution of metaphor from a mere figure of speech to a complex figure of thought, emphasizing its role in shaping meaning and understanding in language. The article discusses the contributions of different theorists, such as Max Black, and examines how metaphors can reflect semantic category errors and cognitive processes. By investigating the interplay between language, thought, and social context, the article reveals the intricate mechanisms of metaphorical transfer and its significance in communication. Additionally, it notes the challenges and questions that arise as researchers strive to decode the complexities of metaphor, indicating a continued need for interdisciplinary study in linguistics, psychology, and sociology. Overall, the article provides a comprehensive overview of the current state of metaphor research and its implications for understanding human cognition and language use.

KEY WORDS: metaphor, cognitive theory, pragmatic approach, conflict theory, anomaly theory, semantic categories, language use.

ANNOTATSIYA: Ushbu maqola kognitiv, pragmatik, konflikt, anomaliya va o'zaro ta'sir nazariyalari kabi turli nazariy nuqtai nazarlar orqali metaforaning ko'p qirrali tabiatini o'rganadi. U metaforaning oddiy nutqiy shakldan murakkab fikr figurasiga aylanishini yoritib beradi, uning tilda ma'no va tushunishni shakllantirishdagi rolini ta'kidlaydi. Maqolada Maks Blek kabi turli nazariyotchilarning hissalarini muhokama qilinadi va metafora semantik toifadagi xatolar va kognitiv jarayonlarni qanday aks ettirishi o'rganiladi. Til, fikr va ijtimoiy kontekst o'rtasidagi o'zaro ta'sirni o'rganish orqali maqola metaforik uzatishning murakkab mexanizmlarini va uning muloqotdagi ahamiyatini ochib beradi. Bundan tashqari, tadqiqotchilar metafora murakkabliklarini dekodlashga intilishlari natijasida yuzaga keladigan qiyinchiliklar va savollarni qayd etadi, bu esa tilshunoslik, psixologiya va sotsiologiyada fanlararo o'rganish zarurligini ko'rsatadi. Umuman olganda, maqola metafora tadqiqotlarining hozirgi holati va uning inson bilimi va tildan foydalanishni tushunishga ta'siri haqida to'liq ma'lumot beradi.

KALIT SO'ZLAR: metafora, kognitiv nazariya, pragmatik yondashuv, konflikt nazariyasi, anomaliya nazariyasi, semantik kategoriyalar, tildan foydalanish.

АННОТАЦИЯ. В этой статье рассматривается многогранная природа метафоры с различных теоретических точек зрения, включая когнитивные, прагматические, конфликтные, аномальные и теории взаимодействия. В ней подчеркивается эволюция метафоры от простой фигуры речи до сложной фигуры мысли, подчеркивая ее роль в

формировании смысла и понимания в языке. В статье обсуждается вклад разных теоретиков, таких как Макс Блэк, и рассматривается, как метафоры могут отражать ошибки семантической категории и когнитивные процессы. Исследуя взаимодействие между языком, мыслью и социальным контекстом, статья раскрывает сложные механизмы метафорического переноса и его значение в коммуникации. Кроме того, в ней отмечаются проблемы и вопросы, которые возникают, когда исследователи стремятся расшифровать сложности метафоры, что указывает на постоянную необходимость междисциплинарного изучения в лингвистике, психологии и социологии. В целом, в статье дается всесторонний обзор текущего состояния исследований метафоры и их последствий для понимания человеческого познания и использования языка.

КЛЮЧЕВЫЕ СЛОВА: метафора, когнитивная теория, прагматический подход, теория конфликта, теория аномалий, семантические категории, использование языка.

INTRODUCTION. Many questions that humanity has encountered throughout evolution, and which continue to captivate researchers, are linked to the acquisition, encoding, storage, and transmission of information. Information taken in from the external environment is actively processed by individuals through thought, relating to various aspects of life. As this information evolves over time, it requires ongoing organization, encoding, and re-encoding to ensure its preservation and future transformation.

METHODOLOGY. This study employs a qualitative approach to examine the multifaceted nature of metaphor through a comprehensive literature review. The methodology involves analyzing existing theoretical frameworks, including cognitive, pragmatic, conflict, anomaly, and interaction theories, to understand their contributions to metaphor research. Primary sources from notable scholars such as Max Black, Aristotle, and various contemporary linguists are systematically reviewed to extract key concepts and insights. Additionally, the study incorporates interdisciplinary perspectives from psychology and sociology to explore the interplay between metaphor, language, and human cognition. Through this integrative approach, the research aims to identify emerging patterns, challenges, and questions in metaphorical studies, contributing to a deeper understanding of metaphorical transfer and its significance in communication.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION. At the core of every effective informational message lies an image and its auditory design, reflecting the conceptual and systemic connections of the surrounding reality. Information received from the external world and stored in memory is organized as a complex system of images, preserved as models, outlines, and patterns. When needed, this information is processed at a verbal level through logical thought patterns developed during cognition. "Words are sensory signs necessary for communication" [1]. During further information processing, logical forms of thought, such as judgments, conclusions, and questions—more complex than individual words or concepts—reveal relationships between objects that cannot be directly derived from sensory experience.

Figurative associations are essential components of thought across all levels of mental activity and in various areas of professional and social life. Whether in daily life, technical and humanitarian fields, or works of fiction, distinct figurative systems are employed, each possessing universal, national, social, or professional significance. Any information, even the

most abstract, can be broken down into visual and figurative elements or communicated through simpler associations.

The vast linguistic diversity that exists today only roughly mirrors the images and systems stored in memory and reflected in an individual's consciousness. With a limited vocabulary, one can generate countless metaphorical meanings, enriched by the subtle nuances of human thought and emotion.

Understanding how sensory and cognitive categories are transformed into language structures, and uncovering the rules governing lexical variation and compatibility based on the nature of the information and communication context, is a key aspect of linguistic research. The aim is to grasp the principles of how reality and human personality evolve as interconnected elements. This requires identifying the processes of translating thoughts into language structures, assessing their correlation, and analyzing these phenomena strictly from a linguistic standpoint. Research on the relationship between language and thought must be supported by parallel investigations and insights from various scientific disciplines.

Metaphor is a subject of scientific research that continually drives advancements in various disciplines. It captures the attention not only of linguists and literary scholars but also of psychologists, philosophers, sociologists, political scientists, and cultural theorists. Metaphor is studied both in terms of its role as a linguistic unit and the mechanisms behind its creation.

Moreover, the process of metaphorization serves as both a linguistic naming tool and a way of conceptualizing the world [2].

The new concepts formed through metaphor in the linguistic worldview merge logical entities of different levels, blending the abstract with the concrete. These concepts arise from the interaction of cognitive processes, empirical experience, cultural context, and the collective's linguistic competence.

The development of the cognitive theory of metaphor, as explored in the works of both domestic and international scholars (N.D. Arutyunova, A.N. Baranov, V.G. Gak, Yu.N. Karaulov, V.N. Telia, G.N. Sklyarevskaya, V.K. Kharchenko, J. Lakoff, M. Johnson, M. Turner, E. McCormack), necessitates the inclusion of extensive practical material. This underscores the relevance of the present study, which seeks to examine metaphor through the lens of cognitive linguistics. In this context, metaphor is linked to specific cognitive structures and is viewed as one of the key mechanisms for understanding the world, reflecting extra-linguistic reality, and expressing aspects of human intelligence through language and thought units.

The cognitive notions of reality embedded in metaphorical transfer are expressed through specific linguistic forms, each carrying distinct semantic, emotional, informational, and stylistic properties, as well as unique functional roles within a sentence. Metaphors emerge when one phenomenon is likened to another based on the semantic similarity of the states, attributes, or actions that define these phenomena. Formally, metaphorical transfer involves using a word (or phrase, sentence) originally intended to describe certain objects or situations to name or characterize other objects or situations, relying on the conditional identity of their attributed predicative features.

Aristotle provided the classical definition of metaphor as a condensed comparison. In modern linguistics, research into the various functional and pragmatic roles that accompany the formation and articulation of metaphor in literary texts has led to the identification of several aspects of its linguistic status: Conceptual – “Metaphor is not merely an unusual way of

using words but a method of artistic world-building, reflecting individual creativity in the subjective content of poetic visions" [3]. Syntactic – “Metaphor is a statement about an object's properties based on its similarity to something previously designated in the reinterpreted meaning of a word” [4]; it is also described as “a transposition of identifying vocabulary, intended to refer to the subject of speech, into the realm of predicates that describe its features and properties” [5]. Semantic – “Metaphor involves the similarity of dissimilarities, the identification of concepts that are broadly contradictory” [6]. Poetic – “Metaphor is a dream, a sleep of language” [7]. Social – “A system of public associations” [8].

In the creation of a metaphor, there are typically two subjects involved: the main (principal) subject of reference and the auxiliary (generalized) subject, which can take explicit or implicit forms. The nature of the auxiliary subject, which conveys the attribute, is determined by the main subject. It's important to note that the simultaneous presence of both subjects is not always evident in comparative constructions. For example, in the sentence "Water runs like from a tub" (I. Krylov), the main object (Water runs (from the hole), like from a tub) is implied but not explicitly stated.

The associative connections formed during metaphorical transfer can be either universal or based on the author's subjective assessment of the phenomena being discussed. The existence of ethnically marked images in language, which form the foundation of phraseological expressions (such as "cunning as a fox" or "cowardly as a hare"), leads to their frequent use in literature to portray characters. Some of these images share similar traits (for example, "free as a bird" or "keen-sighted as an eagle"), while others are specific to particular cultures.

Associative images employed in fiction differ based on the subject of description and the author's pragmatic intentions. The selection of images for comparison is largely influenced by established associations embedded in the minds of native speakers. These images are used to engage the reader with the events described, making the details more relatable and recognizable. For example: "Pierre became even more embarrassed, blushed to tears, as children blush" (L. Tolstoy); "Amalia Ivanovna blushed like a lobster"; "After him ... red as a peony ... entered the ashamed Razumikhin" (F. Dostoevsky); "The samovar's paint crawled down Studzinsky's neck and cheeks" (M. Bulgakov).

In these examples, different images are used to illustrate the degree and nature of blushing: children, lobster, peony, and samovar. Traditionally, the image of a lobster carries a negative connotation, while the image of a child has a consistently positive association in the minds of native speakers. In fiction, flowers are typically linked to youth and beauty. The use of the flower image in this context suggests the hero's youth and inexperience, with the specific reference to a peony likely reflecting the masculine form of the term.

Another image associated with a red face is the comparison to a poppy flower in fiction: "Annushka lit up like a poppy flower" (I. Turgenev); "Yes, thank God, you are healthy! There is no trace of the night's melancholy; your face is like a poppy flower" (A. Pushkin). This same meaning can also be expressed through metaphorical predication: "Suddenly the color rushed into her pale face"; "Suddenly the color flooded her whole face"; "The color hit her in the face again" (F. Dostoevsky).

The variety of associative images corresponding to a predicative feature is influenced by the frequency of that feature's occurrence and its significance. Typically, the range of images used for comparison is limited to a few examples: talkative – magpie, parrot; fast – arrow, storm,

wind; hypocritical – chameleon; hardworking – bee, ant; soulless – doll, car; insensitive – log, block of wood; gloomy – cloud; hard – rock, stone, flint; light – feather, cotton, blade of grass; beautiful – sun, life; soft – wax, clay, etc.

In literary texts, symbolic images correspond to lexemes (such as nouns, verbs, adverbs, etc.), the meanings of which are traditionally associated with these images.

The system of images and symbols ingrained in the consciousness of native speakers, which carry stable meanings and positive or negative connotations, enables the selection of specific options for comparison in each context.

In contemporary studies of metaphor, three primary perspectives on its linguistic nature can be identified:

- Metaphor as a means of existence for the meaning of a word,
- Metaphor as a phenomenon of syntactic semantics,
- Metaphor as a method of conveying meaning within a communicative act.

Along with this, it is necessary to dwell on some general linguistic theories of metaphor that exist in modern domestic and foreign linguistic science.

Emotive theories of metaphor. They traditionally exclude metaphor from scientific and descriptive discourse. These theories deny any cognitive content of metaphor, focusing only on its emotional character; they consider metaphor as a deviation from the linguistic form, devoid of any meaning. This view of metaphor is the result of a logical-positivistic attitude to meaning: the existence of meaning can only be confirmed empirically. Thus, the expression sharp knife has meaning, since this "sharpness" can be verified during tests, but a sharp word could already be considered a completely meaningless combination of words, if not for the semantic shade conveyed exclusively by its emotional coloring.

The concept of tension aligns with the idea that the emotional intensity of a metaphor arises from the unusual combination of its referents [9].

The theory of metaphor as a substitution (substitutive approach) posits that any metaphorical expression can be used in place of a literal equivalent and can be entirely replaced by it. In this view, a metaphor represents the replacement of a correct word with an incorrect one. This perspective is rooted in Aristotle's definition, which suggests that a metaphor assigns a name to something that actually belongs to something else.

The cognitive essence of a metaphor can be viewed as its literal equivalent. In this sense, a metaphor serves as a puzzle for the recipient to decipher. In this form, metaphors rejuvenate old expressions by dressing them in beautiful language [10].

Comparative Theory posits that a metaphor is essentially an elliptical construction, serving as an abbreviated form of a simple or artistic comparison.

According to this theory, the meaning of any metaphorical expression can still be articulated through a literal equivalent, as a literal expression represents one form of explicit comparison. For instance, when we say "this man is a lion," we are essentially asserting "this man is like a lion." This implies that we are comparing all the characteristics of the man with those of a lion to identify the similarities between them. These shared traits form the foundation of the metaphor. Since comparisons can also be literal, the metaphorical definition is assigned a stylistic function.

However, the comparative approach fails to account for the asymmetry inherent in many metaphors. Similarity is generally considered a symmetrical concept; if A is like B, then B should

also be like A. Yet, most metaphors do not demonstrate this symmetry. For example, the metaphor "surgeons are butchers" does not reverse to "butchers are surgeons."

The main issue with the comparative theory is that it relies on literal similarity to explain metaphor without clarifying how that similarity is determined. After all, any two objects can exhibit similarity in various ways, and there are countless options for such similarities. Therefore, the comparative theory of metaphor must elucidate the essence of its fundamental component—similarity.

In contrast, the next theory of metaphor is grounded in dissimilarity and is known as conflict theory, first introduced by M. Beardsley.

According to Beardsley, metaphor serves as a prime example of "self-refuting" discourse; it highlights a specific type of logical contradiction between the subjects of the metaphor. This logical contradiction can be either direct or indirect. For instance, a direct contradiction is evident in the expression "metaphysical streets," as streets are inherently physical. An example of indirect contradiction is found in the phrase "this man is a fox," which implies that it is logically impossible for a person to possess the attributes of both a human and a fox simultaneously [11].

Anomaly theory generalizes several later variations of the previously discussed conflict theory. Proponents of this theory maintain that conflicts and anomalies are intrinsic to metaphor, influencing its identification and understanding. While the nature of the anomaly may vary among its advocates, they all agree that it resembles a semantic category error. Semantic categories classify general types of objects in the world, and a conflict arises when attributes of one object are incorrectly assigned to its opposite. For instance, metaphors that ascribe the qualities of animate objects to inanimate ones violate the established rules of these semantic categories.

Advocates of the anomalous theory argue that such violations of semantic category rules enable the identification of metaphorical expressions as non-literal; however, they differ in their interpretations of these expressions.

The primary issue with conflict theory is that metaphorical conflict is seen as an inherent feature of the words' meanings themselves, independent of context or the author's intentions. In other words, it is a fundamentally formalistic theory. According to this view, metaphor can be recognized and understood without consideration of extralinguistic factors, as it is embedded in "the very structure of meaning" [11]. However, many metaphors do not generate contradictions or violate any semantic categories when examined in isolation. For example, the metaphor "No man is an island" emphasizes that people and islands are not the same, while the metaphor "The old rock is brittle with age" becomes metaphorical only in relation to a specific context, such as describing a cantankerous old geology professor.

Despite their shortcomings, both conflict theory and anomaly theory have significantly contributed to the semantic analysis of metaphor. They address important aspects such as the role of secondary meanings or connotations, as well as the concept of semantic categories and their conflicts. However, both theories fundamentally assert that literal language is more foundational than metaphorical language; they maintain that literal interpretation is primary, with metaphorical interpretation arising only when the literal fails. Consequently, this perspective views metaphor as merely a mistake or a semantic or contextual anomaly, positioning metaphorical meaning as secondary to literal meaning.

The concept of metaphor as interaction, first proposed by Max Black in 1955 in his article "Metaphor" (later included in his book *Models and Metaphor* in 1962 and expanded upon in "More on Metaphor" in 1993), presents a different perspective. Black divides metaphor into two components: a literal main subject (referred to as the tenor by Richards) and a metaphorical auxiliary subject (known as the vehicle). Each of these components has its own conceptual systems, which Black describes as "systems of commonplaces," encompassing a set of properties and associative implications.

Thus, In Black's view, metaphor transcends mere words and encompasses a collection of widely accepted knowledge and associated ideas. It represents the interaction between two conceptual systems, allowing the properties and associations of the auxiliary subject to be applied to the main subject. Consequently, the main subject is examined through the "filter" of the auxiliary system, which selectively emphasizes, obscures, and organizes the defining characteristics of the main subject.

CONCLUSION. The cognitive approach to metaphor has redefined its status, viewing it not merely as a trope or figure of speech but also as a figure of thought. Additionally, the pragmatic approach—which explains the understanding of metaphor through the rules of language use—has paved the way for the development of the activity theory of metaphor.

In the past three decades, linguistic research has shifted its focus toward the functioning of language in speech, as well as the formation and transmission of meaning in utterances, revealing new dimensions of long-studied phenomena, including metaphor. This shift has been furthered by the influence of psychology and sociology, leading to the emergence of interdisciplinary research areas that explore the connection between speech activity, thinking, and human cognitive abilities.

The complexity and multifaceted nature of metaphor make it challenging to identify which of the current perspectives will ultimately play a decisive role in understanding the intricacies of metaphorical transfer. Each new observation or discovery advances researchers toward a solution while simultaneously generating new questions and challenges.

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